

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ORGANIZATION OF DECRYPTION OF A FILE WITH THE HELP OF SYMMETRIC KEYS

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Abstract

In modern times a number of difficulties arise in sending, storing and Receiving Files. One of them is the encryption of symmetric keys to ensure their security.

Keywords: key, encryption, decryption, symmetric system

The study of information security of students and the acquisition of new knowledge, their application with the help of modern technologies remain relevant in the teaching. Thus, the protection of data, data, programs and files is considered important. To do this, they must first protect the files they have created and ensure their secure mutual transfer.

Thus, there are elements that ensure a lot of security in the transfer and reception of the desired file between users. These may include decryption of the file, decryption, selection of the key and application. Here Comes the fact that before sending any file, it must be encrypted. To do this, the encrypted file is encrypted using the key. Many software tools are used for this. These tools are very common and currently used File-Coder software tool. The program consists mainly of 3 parts: file decryption, file decryption free(decryption) and selection of keys.

Let's first consider the issue of encryption. Here you can encrypt any type of file. First you need to select the encrypted file, and then set the location(location) where it will be stored. Here, the selected file can be decrypted 1-100000 times in a cycle.

One of the main issues to be considered is that increasing the number of cycles in this encryption process leads to a decrease in the speed of the encryption process. Determination of the period in the execution of the encryption process is determined by the interest rate in statistical indicators. It displays the state in which the file is executed in the decryption(shown in percentage), how much time is spent on decryption, the current encryption time and the expiration time of the decryption process. After the end of encryption, the file is stored in the selected location, but it is not possible to open and view visitors. We can send this encrypted file to any user.s, but to an increase in reliability. In encryption, a key must be applied to start the process.

If the file is attacked by any misdemeanor in the connection channels, it cannot open the contents of the file without having that key. This is one of the most important tools in ensuring the security of the file[2]. The content of the key here can be only Numbers, only letters, a mixture (letter and accent), a list and all characters. The length of the key can be selected in the form of 64 or 128 floors.

Picture 1. Selection of file encryption

The process of decrypting the file is carried out in contrast to the encryption. Here first the name of the file to be deciphered is written or selected from where it is stored. Then, if you want to name the file to be deciphered with a new name, you give it a new name and save it. For the execution of the decryption process, it

is necessary to add the keyword necessarily. In this case, it is possible to control the current state of the information deciphered during the decryption process. Here, inputs A-F and outputs are also given as A-f in accordance with each input[3].

Picture 2. Selection of file deciphering

A special role in encrypting the file is played by the symmetric key. Here you need to squeeze the key "Select Key" or "file" from the program menu-"select key" to select the key. Select the pre-encrypted file you

need from this drop-down window. It is necessary to select several methods according to the criteria given in the " search methods " block. Characters are selected according to the "list" criteria(Figure 3).

Picture 3. Selection and determination of key

Picture 4. Key finding process

If the password is found correctly, the program displays it on the screen and records how many times the password has been found. In Figure 4, this is listed as the process of finding the key[4]. Since the organization of the encryption of a file with the help of symmetric keys plays an important role in the development of Information Technologies, the procedure for changing the content of the key and encrypting it will help to apply other effective methods in the future.

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